

Wastewater treatment technologies

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ABSTRACT

The article presents an application of multi-criteria analysis for selection of the best treatment technology and the best technical solution to the running of a large and a small wastewater treatment plant. The calculations performed for two plant capacities and for various effluent standards are based on a compromise programming method. The effluent standards considered for the smaller plant are only BOD₅, COD and TSS, while for the larger plant also nitrogen and phosphorus. For each plant's capacity, three different treatment technologies are analyzed. The analyzed technologies included biofilters, continuous and cyclic activated sludge, rotating biological contactors and natural treatment methods. The selection of the best technology is done with a define set of sustainability criteria that can be easily modified and adjusted to specific local conditions. The proposed method can be used for selection of the best treatment technology and the most appropriate technical solution from a sustainability standpoint, at the stage of wastewater system planning and designing, as well as for evaluation of already operating plants.

Keywords: small wastewater treatment plants, technology selection; BOD, COD, TSS

1. INTRODUCTION

Relatively simple wastewater treatment technologies can be designed to provide low cost sanitation and environmental protection while providing additional benefits from the

reuse of water. These technologies use natural aquatic and terrestrial systems. They are in use in a number of locations throughout Latin America and the Caribbean.

These systems may be classified into three principal types, as shown in Figure 1. Mechanical treatment systems, which use natural processes within a constructed environment, tend to be used when suitable lands are unavailable for the implementation of natural system technologies. Aquatic systems are represented by lagoons; facultative, aerated, and hydrograph controlled release (HCR) lagoons are variations of this technology. Further, the lagoon-based treatment systems can be supplemented by additional pre- or post-treatments using constructed wetlands, aquacultural production systems, and/or sand filtration. They are used to treat a variety of wastewaters and function under a wide range of weather conditions. Terrestrial systems make use of the nutrients contained in wastewaters; plant growth and soil adsorption convert biologically available nutrients into less-available forms of biomass, which is then harvested for a variety of uses, including methane gas production, alcohol production, or cattle feed supplements.

Figure 1. Summary of Wastewater Treatment Technologies.

2. MECHANICAL TREATMENT TECHNOLOGIES

Mechanical systems utilize a combination of physical, biological, and chemical processes to achieve the treatment objectives. Using essentially natural processes within an artificial environment, mechanical treatment technologies use a series of tanks, along with

pumps, blowers, screens, grinders, and other mechanical components, to treat wastewaters. Flow of wastewater in the system is controlled by various types of instrumentation. Sequencing batch reactors (SBR), oxidation ditches, and extended aeration systems are all variations of the activated-sludge process, which is a suspended-growth system. The trickling filter solids contact process (TF-SCP), in contrast, is an attached-growth system. These treatment systems are effective where land is at a premium.

3. AQUATIC TREATMENT TECHNOLOGIES

Facultative lagoons are the most common form of aquatic treatment-lagoon technology currently in use. The water layer near the surface is aerobic while the bottom layer, which includes sludge deposits, is anaerobic. The intermediate layer is aerobic near the top and anaerobic near the bottom, and constitutes the facultative zone. Aerated lagoons are smaller and deeper than facultative lagoons. These systems evolved from stabilization ponds when aeration devices were added to counteract odors arising from septic conditions. The aeration devices can be mechanical or diffused air systems. The chief disadvantage of lagoons is high effluent solids content, which can exceed 100 mg/l. To counteract this, hydrograph controlled release (HCR) lagoons are a recent innovation. In this system, wastewater is discharged only during periods when the stream flow is adequate to prevent water quality degradation. When stream conditions prohibit discharge, wastewater is accumulated in a storage lagoon. Typical design parameters are summarized in Table 1.

Table 1. Typical Design Features Aquatic Treatment Units

Technology	Treatment goal	Detention Time (days)	Depth (feet)	Organic Loading (lb/ac/day)
Oxidation pond	Secondary	10-40	3-4.5	36-110
Facultative pond	Secondary	25-180	4.5-7.5	20-60
Aerated pond	Secondary, polishing	7-20	6-18	45-180
Storage pond, HCR pond	Secondary, storage, polishing	100-200	9-15	20-60
Root zone Treatment, Hyacinth pond	Secondary	30-50	<4.5	<45

Source: S.C. Reed, et al., *Natural Systems for Waste Management and Treatment*, New York, McGraw-Hill, 1988.

Constructed wetlands, aquacultural operations, and sand filters are generally the most successful methods of polishing the treated wastewater effluent from the lagoons. These systems have also been used with more traditional, engineered primary treatment technologies

such as Imhoff tanks, septic tanks, and primary clarifiers. Their main advantage is to provide additional treatment beyond secondary treatment where required. In recent years, constructed wetlands have been utilized in two designs: systems using surface water flows and systems using subsurface flows. Both systems utilize the roots of plants to provide substrate for the growth of attached bacteria which utilize the nutrients present in the effluents and for the transfer of oxygen. Bacteria do the bulk of the work in these systems, although there is some nitrogen uptake by the plants. The surface water system most closely approximates a natural wetland. Typically, these systems are long, narrow basins, with depths of less than 2 feet, that are planted with aquatic vegetation such as bulrush (*Scirpus* spp.) or cattails (*Typha* spp.). The shallow groundwater systems use a gravel or sand medium, approximately eighteen inches deep, which provides a rooting medium for the aquatic plants and through which the wastewater flows.

Aquaculture systems are distinguished by the type of plants grown in the wastewater holding basins. These plants are commonly water hyacinth (*Eichhornia crassipes*) or duckweed (*Lemna* spp.). These systems are basically shallow ponds covered with floating plants that detain wastewater at least one week. The main purpose of the plants in these systems is to provide a suitable habitat for bacteria which remove the vast majority of dissolved nutrients. The design features of such systems are summarized in Table 2. (See also section 2.3, in Chapter 2, for a discussion of the role of the plants themselves.).

Table 2. Typical Design Features for Constructed Wetlands.

Design Factor	Surface water flow	Subsurface water flow
Minimum surface area	23-115 ac/mgd	2.3-46 ac/mgd
Maximum water depth	Relatively shallow	Water level below ground surface
Bed depth	Not applicable	12.30 m
Minimum hydraulic residence time	7 days	7 days
Maximum hydraulic loading rate	0.2-1.0 gpd/sq ft	0.5-10 gpd/sq ft
Minimum pretreatment	Primary (secondary optional)	Primary
Range of organic loading as BOD	9-18 lb/ac/d	1.8-140 lb/ac/d

Source: USEPA, *Wastewater Treatment/Disposal for Small Communities*. Cincinnati, Ohio, 1992. (EPA Report No. EPA-625/R-92-005)

Sand filters have been used for wastewater treatment purposes for at least a century in Latin America and the Caribbean. Two types of sand filters are commonly used: intermittent and recirculating. They differ mainly in the method of application of the wastewater. Intermittent filters are flooded with wastewater and then allowed to drain completely before

the next application of wastewater. In contrast, recirculating filters use a pump to recirculate the effluent to the filter in a ratio of 3 to 5 parts filter effluent to 1 part raw wastewater. Both types of filters use a sand layer, 2 to 3 feet thick, underlain by a collection system of perforated or open joint pipes enclosed within graded gravel. Water is treated biologically by the epiphytic flora associated with the sand and gravel particles, although some physical filtration of suspended solids by the sand grains and some chemical adsorption onto the surface of the sand grains play a role in the treatment process. (See also section 2.5, in Chapter 2.)

4. TERRESTRIAL TREATMENT TECHNOLOGIES

Terrestrial treatment systems include slow-rate overland flow, slow-rate subsurface infiltration, and rapid infiltration methods. In addition to wastewater treatment and low maintenance costs, these systems may yield additional benefits by providing water for groundwater recharge, reforestation, agriculture, and/or livestock pasturage. They depend upon physical, chemical, and biological reactions on and within the soil. Slow-rate overland flow systems require vegetation, both to take up nutrients and other contaminants and to slow the passage of the effluent across the land surface to ensure maximum contact times between the effluents and the plants/soils. Slow-rate subsurface infiltration systems and rapid infiltration systems are "zero discharge" systems that rarely discharge effluents directly to streams or other surface waters. Each system has different constraints regarding soil permeability.

Although slow-rate overland flow systems are the most costly of the natural systems to implement, their advantage is their positive impact on sustainable development practices. In addition to treating wastewater, they provide an economic return from the reuse of water and nutrients to produce marketable crops or other agriculture products and/or water and fodder for livestock. The water may also be used to support reforestation projects in water-poor areas. In slow-rate systems, either primary or secondary wastewater is applied at a controlled rate, either by sprinklers or by flooding of furrows, to a vegetated land surface of moderate to low permeability. The wastewater is treated as it passes through the soil by filtration, adsorption, ion exchange, precipitation, microbial action, and plant uptake. Vegetation is a critical component of the process and serves to extract nutrients, reduce erosion, and maintain soil permeability.

Overland flow systems are a land application treatment method in which treated effluents are eventually discharged to surface water. The main benefits of these systems are their low maintenance and low technical manpower requirements. Wastewater is applied intermittently across the tops of terraces constructed on soils of very low permeability and allowed to sheet-flow across the vegetated surface to the runoff collection channel. Treatment, including nitrogen removal, is achieved primarily through sedimentation, filtration, and biochemical activity as the wastewater flows across the vegetated surface of the terraced slope. Loading rates and application cycles are designed to maintain active microorganism growth in the soil. The rate and length of application are controlled to minimize the occurrence of severe anaerobic conditions, and a rest period between applications is needed. The rest period should be long enough to prevent surface ponding, yet short enough to keep

the microorganisms active. Site constraints relating to land application technologies are shown in Table 3.

Table 3. Site Constraints for Land Application Technologies.

Feature	Slow Rate	Rapid Infiltration	Subsurface Infiltration	Overland Flow
Soil texture	Sandy loam to clay loam	Sand and sandy loam	Sand to clayey loam	Silty loam and clayey loam
Depth to groundwater	3 ft	3 ft	3 ft	Not critical
Vegetation	Required	Optional	Not applicable	Required
Climatic restrictions	Growing season	None	None	Growing season
Slope	<20%, cultivated land < 40%, uncultivated land	Not critical	Not applicable	2%-8% finished slopes

Source: USEPA, *Wastewater Treatment/Disposal for Small Communities*. Cincinnati, Ohio, 1992. (EPA Report No. EPA-625/R-92-005)

In rapid infiltration systems, most of the applied wastewater percolates through the soil, and the treated effluent drains naturally to surface waters or recharges the groundwater. Their cost and manpower requirements are low. Wastewater is applied to soils that are moderately or highly permeable by spreading in basins or by sprinkling. Vegetation is not necessary, but it does not cause a problem if present. The major treatment goal is to convert ammonia nitrogen in the water to nitrate nitrogen before discharging to the receiving water.

Subsurface infiltration systems are designed for municipalities of less than 2,500 people. They are usually designed for individual homes (septic tanks), but they can be designed for clusters of homes. Although they do require specific site conditions, they can be low-cost methods of wastewater disposal.

5. ADVANTAGES

Table 4 summarizes the advantages of the various wastewater treatment technologies. In general, the advantages of using natural biological processes relate to their "low-tech/no-tech" nature, which means that these systems are relatively easy to construct and operate, and to their low cost, which makes them attractive to communities with limited budgets. However, their simplicity and low cost may be deceptive in that the systems require frequent inspections and constant maintenance to ensure smooth operation. Concerns include hydraulic overloading, excessive plant growth, and loss of exotic plants to natural watercourses. For this reason, and also because of the land requirements for biologically based technologies, many

communities prefer mechanically-based technologies, which tend to require less land and permit better control of the operation. However, these systems generally have a high cost and require more skilled personnel to operate them.

Table 4. Advantages and Disadvantages of Conventional and Non-conventional Wastewater Treatment Technologies.

Treatment Type	Advantages	Disadvantages
<i>Aquatic Systems</i>		
Stabilization lagoons	Low capital cost Low operation and maintenance costs Low technical manpower requirement	Requires a large area of land May produce undesirable odors
Aerated lagoons	Requires relatively little land area Produces few undesirable odors	Requires mechanical devices to aerate the basins Produces effluents with a high suspended solids concentration
<i>Terrestrial Systems</i>		
Septic tanks	Can be used by individual households Easy to operate and maintain Can be built in rural areas	Provides a low treatment efficiency Must be pumped occasionally Requires a landfill for periodic disposal of sludge and septage
Constructed wetlands	Removes up to 70% of solids and bacteria Minimal capital cost Low operation and maintenance requirements and costs	Remains largely experimental Requires periodic removal of excess plant material Best used in areas where suitable native plants are available
<i>Mechanical Systems</i>		
Filtration systems	Minimal land requirements; can be used for household-scale treatment Relatively low cost Easy to operate	Requires mechanical devices
Vertical biological reactors	Highly efficient treatment method Requires little land area Applicable to small communities for local-scale treatment and to big cities for regional-scale treatment	High cost Complex technology Requires technically skilled manpower for operation and maintenance Needs spare-parts-availability Has a high energy requirement
Activated sludge	Highly efficient treatment method Requires little land area Applicable to small communities for	High cost Requires sludge disposal area (sludge is usually land-spread)

	local-scale treatment and to big cities for regional-scale treatment	Requires technically skilled manpower for operation and maintenance
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6. DISADVANTAGES

Table 4 also summarizes the disadvantages of the various wastewater treatment technologies. These generally relate to the cost of construction and ease of operation. Mechanical systems can be costly to build and operate as they require specialized personnel. Nevertheless, they do offer a more controlled environment which produces a more consistent quality of effluent. Natural biological systems, on the other hand, are more land-intensive, require less-skilled operators, and can produce effluents of variable quality depending on time of year, type of plants, and volume of wastewater loading. Generally, the complexity and cost of wastewater treatment technologies increase with the quality of the effluent produced.

7. CONCLUSIONS

The effluent standards considered for the smaller plant are only BOD₅, COD and TSS while for the larger plant also nitrogen and phosphorus. For each plant's capacity the three different treatment technologies are analyzed. The analyzed technologies included biofilters, continuous and cyclic activated sludge, rotating biological contactors and natural treatment methods. The selection of the best technology is done with a define set of sustainability criteria that can be easily modified and adjusted to specific local conditions. The proposed method can be used for selection of the best treatment technology and the technical solution at the stage of wastewater system planning and designing as well as for evaluation of already operated plants from sustainability standpoint.

Mechanical treatment systems, which use natural processes within a constructed environment, tend to be used when suitable lands are unavailable for the implementation of natural system technologies. Aquatic systems are represented by lagoons; facultative, aerated, and hydrograph controlled release (HCR) lagoons are variations of this technology. Further, the lagoon-based treatment systems can be supplemented by additional pre- or post-treatments using constructed wetlands, aquacultural production systems, and/or sand filtration. They are used to treat a variety of wastewaters and function under a wide range of weather conditions. Terrestrial systems make use of the nutrients contained in wastewaters; plant growth and soil adsorption convert biologically available nutrients into less-available forms of biomass, which is then harvested for a variety of uses, including methane gas production, alcohol production, or cattle feed supplements.

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